

METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF ROSUVASTATIN CALCIUM BY USING UV VISIBLE SPECTROSCOPY

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Abstract

The aim of study is to develop a new , rapid and highly sensitive UV Visible spectrophotometer method for development and validation for the estimation of Rosuvastatin calium. Chloroform was selected as the suitable solvent based on solubility studies. The λ_{max} was found to be 243 nm. Linearity was established over a concentration range of 2-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with a correlation coefficient of 0.999. Accuracy studies was showed a mean recovery of 100.19% with % RSD of 0.39% Precision, robustness and ruggedness were confirmed with %RSD values below 2%. The method demonstrated high sensitivity with LOD, LOQ values of 0.037 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 0.116 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively. Thus the method is validated as per ICH guidelines and is suitable for routine analysis of Rosuvastatin in Bulk and tablet dosage forms.

Introduction

Spectroscopy

It is a Branch of Science that deals with the study of the interaction of matter with light or Electromagnetic Radiation. It is the measurement and interpretation of Electromagnetic radiation absorbed or emitted when the molecules or atoms or ions of sample move from one energy state to another. Ultraviolet (UV) and visible radiation comprise only a small part of the electromagnetic spectrum, which includes such other forms of radiation as radio, infrared (IR), cosmic, and X rays.

DRUG PROFILE

Rosuvastatin Calcium

Description:

Rosuvastatin Calcium is a lipid-lowering agent that belongs to the statin class. It works by inhibiting HMG-CoA reductase, the enzyme responsible for cholesterol synthesis in the liver. It is used to treat high cholesterol and related conditions and to prevent cardiovascular disease.

Chemical Structure of Rosuvastatin Calcium

Molecular Formula: C₄₄H₅₄CaF₂N₆O₁₂S₂

Solubility: Practically insoluble in water, soluble in methanol and ethanol

Melting Point: Approx. 155°C (decomposes)

pK_a Values: 4.6 (carboxylic acid), 9.5 (hydroxyl group)

Uses:

Rosuvastatin is indicated for the treatment of primary hyperlipidemia and mixed dyslipidemia, including familial hypercholesterolemia (both heterozygous and homozygous types). It is also used in the prevention of cardiovascular events such as stroke and myocardial infarction in patients with elevated risk factors.

Marketed Formulations:

Brand Names: Crestor, Rosuvas, Rozavel

Dose: Commonly available in 5 mg, 10 mg, 20 mg tablet

MATERIALS AND METHODS

CHEMICALS USED:

Chemicals Name	Supplier
Rosuvastatin calcium	Aurobindo pharma Ltd
Acetonitrile	Vijay enterprises
Chloroform	Vijay enterprises
Methanol	Vijay enterprises

Table 4.1:Chemicals Name

INSTRUMENTS USED:

Instrument name	Model name
Uv visible spectrophotometer	SHIMADZU (model UV-1800)
Analytical balance	SHIMADZU ATX224R
Ultra sonicator	Sonica®2200MH

Table: 4.2 : Instruments Used

METHOD DEVELOPMENT**Selection of solvent:**

Method development includes choosing an appropriate solvent for the procedure which can be the best for precise results, accuracy and cost efficient. By testing distilled water, methanol, n hexane, chloroform and acetonitrile. Drug is soluble in chloroform. Apparently chloroform is best for solubility.

Solubility studies:

Solubility studies help identify a **solvent or solvent system** in which the drug (like Rosuvastatin) is sufficiently soluble. This ensures **complete dissolution**, which is essential for accurate and consistent analysis.

Selection of Wavelength

The absorbance of the solution containing Rosuvastatin at 10µg/ml was determined in UV range 200-400nm using an appropriate blank. 10µg/ml was prepared by dissolving 10mg of Rosuvastatin in 100ml diluent (Stock A). 1ml was pipetted out and dissolved in 10ml diluent to obtain 10 µg/ml solution. The λ_{max} was found to be 243nm.

Preparation of Standard Solution

- **Preparation of Rosuvastatin Standard Solution:** Weigh accurately about 10 mg and transfer in to a 100 ml volumetric flask. Add 30 ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve. Dilute up to mark with diluent.) Filter through 0.45µm nylon membrane filter.
- **Preparation of Test Solution:** Determine the average weight of 10 tablets, Powdered it. Weigh accurately about 10 mg of Rosuvastatin calcium tablet powder (equivalent to 10 mg of Rosuvastatin calcium) and transfer in to a 100ml volumetric flask. Add 30 ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve. Dilute up to mark with diluent. Filter the solution through 0.45µm nylon membrane filter.

METHOD VALIDATION

Specificity:

- The specificity is established by recording the UV Spectrum from 200 nm to 400 nm for blank, Rosuvastatin shows maximum absorbance at **243.0 nm**, as confirmed by the spectrum overlay and individual spectrum data.
- standard, and Sample preparations. It is observed that there is no interference between the absorbance in the UV spectrum of Rosuvastatin shows maximum absorbance at **243.0 nm**, as confirmed by the spectrum overlay and individual spectrum data.

Linearity

- Linearity was determined by plotting concentration against corresponding absorbance. A standard solution was further diluted with buffer to obtain 2 µg/ml to 10 µg/ml range solutions. The calibration curves were constructed by plotting absorbance versus concentration and the regression equations were calculated.

Accuracy:

- The accuracy of the proposed method was assessed by recovery studies which were carried out at three different levels i.e 50%,100% and 150%. A known amount of standard drug solution was added to the pre analyzed sample solution at three different levels, was absorbance was recorded. The % recovery was then calculated.
- **Preparation of Rosuvastatin Standard Solution:** Weigh accurately about 10 mg and transfer in to a 100 ml volumetric flask. Add 30 ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve. Dilute up to mark with diluent.) Filter through 0.45µm nylon membrane filter.
- **Preparation of Test Solution:** Determine the average weight of 10 tablets, Powdered it. Weigh accurately about 10 mg of Rosuvastatin calcium tablet powder (equivalent to 10 mg of Rosuvastatin calcium) and transfer in to a 100ml volumetric flask. Add 30 ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve. Dilute up to mark with diluent. Filter the solution through 0.45µm nylon membrane filter.

Precision:

- **Intra-day precision:** standard stock solutions were taken in a 10 ml volumetric flasks and final volume was made up to mark. The absorbances of these solutions were individually measured thrice within a day.
- **Inter day precision:** standard stock solutions were taken in 10 ml volumetric flasks and volume were made up to mark. The absorbances of these solutions were measured thrice in three days and recorded.

Robustness:

Small deliberate changes in the method like change in wavelength are made but there were no recognized change in the result and are within range as per ICH guidelines.

Change in wavelength:

(normal experimental condition:243nm)

Robustness conditions like wavelength minus (241nm), wavelength plus(245nm), were maintained and samples were injected in duplicate manner System sustainability parameters were not much affected and all the parameters were passed. %RSD was within the limit

Ruggedness:

Six test solutions of Rosuvastatin, were prepared as per the analytical method on different labs. These test solutions were analysed by a different analyst using different UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The % RSD of % drug release results of twelve test solutions (six samples from method precision and six samples from intermediate precision) was calculated.

LOD & LOQ:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3\sigma / S$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 / S,$$

Where,

σ is the standard deviation of the blank and

S is the slope of the calibration plot

Assay: Assay was performed with the Rosuvastatin Calcium formulation.

Label claim: 10.0 mg

Results and Discussion

Solubility studies:

Table no. 5.1 solubility studies

Solvent	Solubility
Distilled water	Insoluble
N hexane	Insoluble
Acetonitrile	Soluble
Methanol	Insoluble
Chloroform	Soluble

Selection of wavelength:

Figure no:5.2. Selection of wavelength

The λ_{max} was found to be 243nm.

METHOD VALIDATION

1. Specificity / Selectivity:

S.No.	Absorbance of Rosuvastatin in 243 nm
1	0.334
2	0.332
3	0.330
4	0.331
5	0.336
Mean	0.333
Standard Deviation (±)	0.002
(%) Relative Standard Deviation	0.6

Table 1: Selectivity results

No absorption spectra obtained for blank preparations at 243 nm in the UV spectrum.

One Absorption spectra observed at 243 nm for Rosuvastatin standard and sample preparations.

Remarks:

The method is specific.

2. Linearity

Linearity Level	Sample	Absorbance	Correlation
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	Conc (in mg/ml)		Coefficient
Level – 1	0	0	
Level – 2	2	0.165	
Level – 3	4	0.331	
Level – 4	6	0.496	
Level – 5	8	0.659	
Level – 6	10	0.825	

Table 5.2: Results of linearity of standard

3.Accuracy (% Recovery):

Level of Addition	Recovery (%)
First Level (Rec-50 %)	100.17
Third Level (Rec-100 %)	100.59
Fifth Level (Rec-150%)	99.81
Mean	100.19
Standard Deviation (±)	0.3906
(%) Relative Standard Deviation	0.39

Table –5. 3: Accuracy (%Recovery) – results

Remarks:

The percentage recovery for Rosuvastatin at each level lies between 98.0% and 102.0%. % RSD at each recovery level is less than 2.0%.

The analytical method meets the pre-established acceptance criteria for recovery study as per protocol.

Hence, it is concluded that the method is accurate.

4. Precision**Intraday Precision**

Sr. No.	Absorbance of Rosuvastatin in 243 nm
1	0.331
2	0.336
3	0.333
4	0.337
5	0.329
Mean	0.333
Standard Deviation (±)	0.003
(%) Relative Standard Deviation	0.6

Table.5.4 Intraday precision

Interday Precision

Sr. No.	Absorbance of Rosuvastatin in 243 nm
1	0.338
2	0.335
3	0.337
4	0.336
5	0.335
Mean	0.336
Standard Deviation (±)	0.001
(%) Relative Standard Deviation	0.299

Table – 5.5: Interday Precision

Remarks: The % RSD of the twelve drug release results is found to be more than 2.0%. Thus, the method is found to be precise.

5.0 Robustness:

S.No.	Absorbance of Rosuvastatin	
	241nm	245nm
1	0.332	0.335
2	0.334	0.331
Mean	0.33	0.33
Standard Deviation (±)	0.00	0.00
(%) Relative Standard Deviation	0.33	0.65

Table – 5.6: Robustness with change in wavelength

Wavelength →	228nm	232nm
Sample	% Assay	
Test solution	99.34	99.57
Avg % drug release result from method precision	100.49	100.49
Mean	99.92	100.03
Standard Deviation (±)	0.81	0.65
(%) Relative Standard Deviation	0.82	0.65

Table – 5.7: Results for change in wavelength

Remarks: The % RSD of the six drug release results is found less than 2.0% and meets the pre-established acceptance criteria. Hence, it is concluded that the method is robust.

6. Ruggedness

I) Different Analysts

Analyst – 1

S.No.	Absorbance of Rosuvastatin in 243nm
1	0.332
2	0.335
3	0.331

4	0.336
5	0.330
Mean	0.333
Standard Deviation (±)	0.003
(%) Relative Standard Deviation	0.6

Table-5.8 Results for ruggedness by analyst-1**Remark:**

The % RSD of the five drug release results is found less than 2.0% and meets the pre-established acceptance criteria. Hence, it is concluded that the method is rugged.

Analyst – 2

Sr. No.	Absorbance of Rosuvastatin in 243 nm
1	0.332
2	0.335
3	0.331
4	0.336
5	0.330
Mean	0.333
Standard Deviation (±)	0.003
(%) Relative Standard Deviation	0.6

Table- 5.9 Results for ruggedness by analyst-2**Remark :**

The % RSD of the six drug release results is found less than 2.0% and meets the pre-established acceptance criteria. Hence, it is concluded that the method is precise.

II) Different labs**Lab -I**

Sr. No.	Absorbance of Rosuvastatin at 243nm
1	0.336
2	0.333

3	0.334
4	0.338
5	0.334
Mean	0.335
Standard Deviation (±)	0.003
(%) Relative Standard Deviation	0.6

Table- 5.10 Results for ruggedness in Lab-I

Lab-II

Sr. No.	Absorbance of Rosuvastatin at 243nm
1	0.332
2	0.335
3	0.331
4	0.336
5	0.330
Mean	0.333
Standard Deviation (±)	0.003
(%) Relative Standard Deviation	0.6

Table- 5.11 Results for ruggedness in Lab-II

7.LOD and LOQ

LOD Value	0.037
LOQ Value	0.116

Table-5.12 Results of LOD and LOQ

Conclusion

The present study aimed to develop and validate a simple, accurate, precise, and robust UV-spectrophotometric method for the estimation of Rosuvastatin calcium in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations. The solubility studies revealed that Rosuvastatin is soluble in acetonitrile and chloroform, while it remains insoluble in distilled water, methanol, and n-hexane. This solubility profile guided the selection of acetonitrile as the suitable solvent for UV analysis. The wavelength of maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) for Rosuvastatin was found to

be 243 nm, which was used throughout the method due to its sensitivity and lack of interference.

Validation of the developed method was carried out as per ICH guidelines. The method showed excellent specificity, as no absorbance was observed for blank solutions at 243 nm, confirming no interference from excipients or solvents. Linearity was established over the concentration range of 2–10 mg/mL with a correlation coefficient of 0.999, indicating a strong linear relationship between absorbance and concentration. Accuracy studies conducted through recovery tests at three levels (50%, 100%, and 150%) demonstrated recovery values between 98–102% and %RSD of only 0.39%, confirming that the method is highly accurate.

Robustness was demonstrated by small changes in wavelength (241 nm and 245 nm), with consistent results and %RSD values below 2%, proving the method's stability under slight variations. Ruggedness was assessed by different analysts and laboratories, and in all cases, %RSD values remained within acceptable limits, confirming that the method is reliable across different environments and operators. Furthermore, the method demonstrated good sensitivity with a low limit of detection (LOD) of 0.037 mg/mL and a limit of quantitation (LOQ) of 0.116 mg/mL.

In conclusion, the developed UV-spectrophotometric method for Rosuvastatin is simple, rapid, cost-effective, and highly reliable. It meets all the required validation criteria including specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness, ruggedness, LOD, and LOQ. Therefore, it can be confidently applied for the routine quantitative analysis of Rosuvastatin in bulk drug substances and pharmaceutical dosage forms in quality control laboratories.

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